

Some hints on an extended version of the 4/2 stochastic volatility model

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Introduction

We develop a modified version of the mean-reverting 4/2 stochastic volatility model introduced in Escobar-Anel & Gong (2020) where jumps are allowed in the asset price dynamics, and the drift coefficient may also switch between regimes related to a sentiment indicator. In this framework, we develop the distributional characteristics of asset returns, suggest a numerical procedure for model estimation, and illustrate some preliminary results on the pricing of European options.

Methods

By applying classical measure transformations, we prove the existence of a pricing measure which guarantees absence of arbitrage opportunities in the market under analysis and allows the computation of European option prices. Under suitable assumptions on the model parameters, we also derive main distributional characteristics of asset returns and suggest a numerical procedure to estimate the parameters. An extensive simulation study is finally carried out to assess the performance of the estimation technique.

Results

The main theoretical contributions of this study are:

1. the derivation of an equivalent martingale measure ensuring absence of arbitrage in the market;
2. the computation of a semiclosed expression for the conditional characteristic function of the logarithmic prices under both the physical and risk-neutral probability measures;
3. the introduction of an estimation for the suggested model.

A numerical illustration is also provided by fitting the proposed model on empirical data for the Gold and Crude Oil markets.

References

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